

Speaking as proxy for nature

Game materials

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Role card

You represent the Meadow of the River _____.

The Meadow is a complex ecosystem of plants and animals. As it connects neighboring ecosystems, it is a vital ecological corridor through which animals and plants can spread. The meadow is also an important resting place for migratory birds and essential for cooling and fresh air in summer. It is flooded during high water. Over the years, there has been an increase in infrastructure that gets labelled as "green" and changes the shape and form of the Meadow. It is like death by a thousand cuts! The drainage pattern changes, the meadow grass decreases and concrete gets poured everywhere. There is less life, both above and underground, only more sterile infrastructure.

How to defend the integrity of the Meadow and make her voice heard?

Most important needs/ interests (personal notes)

Role card

You represent Dogs and their Parents who visit the meadows almost daily.

Here they can move freely, away from all the traffic. Sometimes the dog is a protector, sometimes a good mate, and sometimes as silly as a small child: anyone who lets a dog into their life has a constant companion in everyday life. As pack animals, dogs are reluctant to leave their parents' side. This ability to build relationships has developed over thousands of years. Humans have lived closely with four-legged friends for at least 15,000 years — longer than with any other animal. If this area is closed off by a solar farm, they would have to go back to walking on concrete streets and dangerous roads.

What do you think should be done to bring their concerns forward?

Most important needs/ interests (personal notes)

Role card

You represent the Oat Grass.

The oat grass grows in loose clumps along the River _____. It forms dense root carpets and protects the soil from erosion, and is an important habitat for small mammals and many insects. An entire biotic community with a rich diversity of species has formed around the oats, which is reduced by the input of nutrients. Under the oat grass, the soil creates a humus layer and thus stores carbon. The wind and the sun are its best friend and help it to propagate. That's why oat grass grows so well on the meadow. In full sun! The solar farm will, ironically, change this. The shadow of the panels is not suitable for the oat grass. They might also plant some shade loving plants here and disrupt the oat grass's habitat.

How to stand up for the rights of the Oat Grass?

Most important needs/ interests (personal notes)

Role card

You stand up for the interests of the Beaver.

They have been living on these banks for generations. The beaver loves to chew on the wood in the side streams and to sometimes swim to the other shore and explore the area. They can shape river landscapes and regulate the water level by building dams. The waters then flow more slowly and their water surface becomes larger. In this way, the beaver creates a favorable habitat for itself and for many other water dwellers. After they were almost extinct, their numbers are increasing again and they need space. But space is so hard to find if more infrastructure projects come in and change the habitat!

How will you defend the Beaver's right to stay?

Most important needs/ interests (personal notes)

Role card

You are an advocate for the interests of the Sheep and Shepherds.

Grazing with sheep is an extensive form of landscape management. It protects the ecosystem of the meadows because it prevents trees and shrubs from growing on the meadow. Grazing creates species-rich landscapes, which can best be preserved if this utilization is maintained. The sheep visit the Elbe meadow each year, from spring to fall, to enjoy the delicious oat grass. They also enjoy the open views and the cool breeze from the river. When it gets too hot, there is always cool water in the area for the sheep. It will be a pity to go back to dry proceed grass in the shed.

How to put forward the interests of the Sheep and Shepherds?

Most important needs/ interests (personal notes)

Role card

You are an advocate for the Cuckoo.

The birds live in the meadow every summer. Here they always find something to eat: spiders, earthworms, caterpillars, and snails. This is important when they nest in the nearby trees in summer and prepare for winter. However, each year it has been getting hard to find food and a space to nest. The cuckoos have already seen a lot on their travels, they are witnesses to climate change. The fact that spring is starting earlier in Central Europe is becoming their fate. By the time the cuckoo arrives here from its long journey and has mated, many host birds are already sitting on their eggs and ready to breed. Now, this solar farm here might further reduce their options.

How to make the city see the point of view of the Cuckoos?

Most important needs/ interests (personal notes)

Rolefinding Poem

An evening in September. A walk along the Elbe.

The warm autumn light falls gently on the grass in the meadow.

Small insects dance in the air.

The Elbe shimmers like velvet and gently evokes the magic of the landscape.

The meadows are still green and the trees still have leaves. The sun warms a little and kisses away the first cool moments. The world seems almost light-hearted in this place.

A soft intake of breath - a snort - and a croak.

The cold winter is still a long way off. The sunset seems almost endless today. Carried by the shadow of summer, it warms the meadows from afar with gentle power.

Golden yellow light shines on the people, animals and plants, enveloping everything in a soft glow. The river flows gently, like a painting.

What has changed in all this time?

Where have the memories gone?

How do we want to live in the onrushing time?

And on we go. Always following the stream.

We let ourselves drift with the flow of time as we are beings in the wind.

Storyline

Mobile Solar Panels next to river _____

_____ (name of city) is facing major changes. The urban river landscape of the _____ (name of river) with its vast, unspoiled meadows is to be used for a variety of purposes. A technical innovation makes this possible: large-scale mobile solar panels are to be set up on the meadows during the summer months to produce electricity for the climate-neutral city.

Interest groups have already come together to speak out in favor of the project and drive it forward. However, critical voices are also becoming louder in the city. To take this conflict into account, the city planning office and the environmental office of the city have commissioned a private planning office to conduct a planning workshop on this project.

The aim of this planning workshop is to incorporate the interests and ideas of the various stakeholders into the planning process. During the workshop, ideas for the use and design of the planning area will be collected, discussed and spatially localized. In order to make the proposals visible, maps of the planning area are laid out on which the stakeholders can draw their proposals directly. The finished sketches will be presented at the end of the workshop. After the planning workshop, the sketched ideas will be put up for public discussion and will then be included in the city council's further political decision-making process.

